

from their respective formation curves of the metal complex-ion equilibria, which correspond to pL values at $\bar{n}=0.5$ and $\bar{n}=1.5$ respectively.

The most representative values are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS

Cations	$t=25^{\circ}\text{C}$		$\mu=0.1M$				
	H^+	UO_2^{2+}	Cu^{2+}	Zn^{2+}	Co^{2+}	Ni^{2+}	Mg^{2+}
$\log K_1$	9.90	9.25	8.77	5.87	5.45	5.97	4.07
$\log K_2$	2.48	7.50	—	—	—	—	—

The order of stability of bivalent metal chelates studied was

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to record their sincere thanks to Dr. D.G. Vartak, B.A.R.C., Bombay and Dr. R.A. Kulkarni, Principal, Ramnarain Ruia College, Bombay-400 019, for their valuable suggestions and continuous encouragement.

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Determination of Stability Constants of 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene-3'-Methoxyaniline with Some Divalent Metal Ions

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Manuscript received 28 August 1978, revised 20 January 1979; accepted 6 June 1979

IN continuation of our earlier studies on the complexes of Schiff bases we report here the stability constants of Cu(II), Zn(II), Ni(II), Co(II) and Mg(II) with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-3'-methoxyaniline determined potentiometrically following the Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹.

Experimental

pH measurements were carried out on a Corning model 12, precision research pH meter equipped

with wide range glass and calomel electrodes. The meter has an arrangement for normal and expanded scale on which changes in pH can be measured with an accuracy of 0.005 pH unit.

The ligand was synthesised and repeatedly crystallised to get an analytically pure sample². The dioxane used was purified by the method described by Vogel³. Distilled water redistilled over alkaline potassium permanganate was used throughout the investigation.

The medium of titration was a 75 : 25 per cent (v/v) dioxane-water mixture in which the ionic strength was maintained at 0.1 M NaClO_4 . The preparation and standardisation of metal solutions together with details of the potentiometric titrations are the same as have been reported in an earlier communication⁴. The experimental method of Irving and Rossotti was applied to determine the values of $\bar{n}$ and pL .

Results and Discussion

In the ligand it is the chelated phenolic 'OH' group which takes part in the complex formation and the proton is replaced from it by the metal ion during chelation. Since only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated during complexation, Y , the number of dissociable protons attached to each ligand molecule is one.

From the titration curves using (i) and (ii), $\bar{n}_A$ values at various 'B' values (pH meter readings) were calculated and the corresponding $\bar{n}_A$ values were plotted. The formation curve extends over a range $0.3 < \bar{n}_A < 1.64$ and is wavelike. The value of $pK_1^H=9.70$ was evaluated from the half integral point at $\bar{n}_A=0.5$ while that of $pK_2^H=3.04$ was obtained at $\bar{n}_A=1.5$.

From the titration curves of solutions (ii) and (iii) $\bar{n}$ and pL values were evaluated. The $\bar{n}$ values were plotted against the corresponding pL values to get the formation curves of the metal complex-ion equilibria. From these curves the values of stability constants, $\log K_1$ which correspond to pL values at $\bar{n}=0.5$ were computed. These were: 8.90, 5.70, 5.56, 5.46 and 3.82 for the respective metals and are in agreement with the Irving and Williams order⁵ viz. $\text{Cu} > \text{Zn} > \text{Ni} > \text{Co} > \text{Mg}$.

There is a relatively large difference between the $\log K_1$ values for the copper chelate and those for the chelates of other metals. The higher stability of the copper chelate may be due to the formation of a square-planar complex. The $\log K_1$ value for zinc is not much greater than that of nickel; $M-L\pi$ interaction between the π -orbitals of zinc and the ligand is therefore negligible.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to record their sincere thanks to Dr. D. G. Vartak, B. A. R. C., Bombay, for his valuable suggestions and to Dr. R. A. Kulkarni, Principal, Ramnarain Ruia College, Bombay, for his kind interest and encouragement.

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Polarographic Study of the Composition and Stability Constants of Thallium(I) and Indium(III) N-Glycylglycine Complexes

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Manuscript received 10 November 1978, revised 28 February 1979, accepted 6 June 1979

ON account of the increased significance of the sulphur containing organic compounds¹⁻⁵ and amino acids in pharmaceutical and industrial field, considerable interest regarding their electrochemical behaviour has been shown in the past two decades.

This communication reports the polarographic determination of the composition and stability constants of Tl(I) and In(III) complexes with N-glycylglycine at 30° and 40°.

Experimental

N-glycylglycine (NH₂CH₂CONH CH₂COOH) was supplied by B.D.H. Chemicals Ltd. Poole, England and all other chemicals used were of AnalaR B.D.H. grade.

In case of Tl(I) N-glycylglycine complexes, the concentration of metal ion was 1.0 mM in the presence of 0.1M NaClO₄ and 0.002% Triton-X-100 at pH=3.8 (maintained by HClO₄ and NaOH). The concentration of ligand was varied from 0.04 to 0.12M.

In case of In(III) N-glycylglycine complexes, the concentration of metal ion was 0.5 mM in the presence of 0.1M NaClO₄ and 0.002% Triton-X-100.

The concentration of ligand was varied from 0.04 to 0.12M.

Toshniwal polarograph in conjunction with a thermostated H-cell was used for recording the current-voltage curves. The capillary used had the following characteristics in 0.1M supporting electrolyte (NaClO₄); m=2.953 mg/sec., t=2.5 sec/drop at h=43.5 cm and -0.4 V vs S.C.E.

Results and Discussion

The current-voltage curves of Tl(I) and In(III) in presence of different concentrations of N-glycylglycine are plotted at 30° and 40°. In each case a single well defined cathodic wave appeared. All the plots of log (i/i_d-i) vs -E_{d,e.} yielded straight lines and the slopes agreed with the reversibility of the reduction. The cathodic shift in E_{1/2} coupled with decrease in diffusion current on increasing N-glycylglycine concentration shows the complex formation with Tl(I) and In(III) ions, respectively. The plot of i_d vs h_{eff}^{1/2} was found to be linear, indicating the diffusion controlled nature of the reduction of Tl(I) and In(III) complexes.

The curvature obtained in the plot of -E_{1/2} vs -log C_x showed the successive complex formation and hence the method of DeFord and Hume^{6,7} was adopted for deriving various functions F₁(X). From the experimental data, the complexity function F₁(X) which is polynomial in (X), is set up; the coefficients of the latter are required, β_n. The graphical extrapolation reduces the polynomial equation to N-equations from which the corresponding β_n are obtained and are given below :

Tl(I)N-glycylglycine complexes

$$\beta_1 = 6, \quad \beta_2 = 11, \quad \beta_3 = 920 \text{ at } 30^\circ \\ \text{and } \beta_1 = 4, \quad \beta_2 = 5, \quad \beta_3 = 740 \text{ at } 40^\circ$$

In(III) N-glycylglycine complexes

$$\beta_1 = 2, \quad \beta_2 = 100, \quad \beta_3 = 9400 \text{ at } 30^\circ \\ \text{and } \beta_1 = 4, \quad \beta_2 = 120, \quad \beta_3 = 8800 \text{ at } 40^\circ$$

Acknowledgement

We thank the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, Delhi, for a Research Scholarship to one of us (S.P.B.) and Principal for providing research facilities.

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